

"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT"

IV GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI: "O'ZBEKISTON - 2030" STRATEGIYASI

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2025

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MAXSUS SON

- MACROECONOMIC STABILITY
•LABOR MARKET IN THE GREEN ECONOMY
•GLOBAL ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC RELATIONS
•GREEN INVESTMENT AND FINANCING
•GREEN TECHNOLOGIES
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CONFERENCE "GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC TRENDS"

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2030

BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMI VA XUSUSIY SEKTORNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI

**TOSHKENT DAVLAT
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(MAXSUS SON)

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BIOTECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS IN URBAN PLANNING: OPPORTUNITIES AND LIMITATIONS OF “LIQUID TREES”

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Abstract: This article explores the innovative project “Liquid Trees” (Liquid 3), created by researchers at the University of Belgrade as a modern alternative to traditional urban greening. The system consists of bioreactors with microalgae (*Chlorella vulgaris*), which absorb carbon dioxide and generate oxygen much more efficiently than ordinary plants. A single unit can match the oxygen output of two mature trees or 200 m² of lawn, while also producing valuable biomass for agriculture, biofuel, and pharmaceuticals.

Key words: Liquid Trees, environmental issues, green economy, high technologies, urban life quality, soil enrichment, erosion, groundwater, appearance.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada Belgrad universiteti olimlari tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan “Suyuq daraxtlar” (Liquid 3) loyihasi — an’anaviy shahar ko’kalamzorlashtirishiga zamonaviy alternativ sifatida o’rganiladi. Ushbu tizim mikroalgalar (*Chlorella vulgaris*) joylashtirilgan bioreaktorlardan iborat bo’lib, ular karbonat angidridni yutadi va oddiy o’simliklarga nisbatan ancha samarali tarzda kislorod ishlab chiqaradi. Bir dona modul ikki tup katta daraxt yoki 200 m² maysazor kislorod ishlab chiqarish hajmiga teng keladi, shu bilan birga qishloq xo’jaligi, biotoplar va farmatsevtika uchun qimmatli biomassa ham yaratadi.

Kalit so’zlar: Suyuq daraxtlar, ekologik muammolar, yashil iqtisodiyot, yuqori texnologiyalar, shahar hayoti sifati, tuproqni boyitish, eroziya, yer osti suvlari, tashqi ko’rinish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается инновационный проект «Жидкие деревья» (Liquid 3), разработанный исследователями Белградского университета как современная альтернатива традиционному городскому озеленению. Система представляет собой биореакторы с микроводорослями (*Chlorella vulgaris*), которые поглощают углекислый газ и вырабатывают кислород значительно эффективнее обычных растений. Один модуль способен заменить кислородный эффект двух взрослых деревьев или 200 м² газона, одновременно производя ценную биомассу для сельского хозяйства, биотоплива и фармацевтики.

Ключевые слова: Жидкие деревья, экологические проблемы, зелёная экономика, высокие технологии, качество городской жизни, обогащение почвы, эрозия, подземные воды, внешний вид.

INTRODUCTION

“High-quality greening” is an integral component of urban improvement. Greening in cities serves a multitude of purposes simultaneously, with the most critical one being the improvement of the environmental situation. Plants produce oxygen essential for respiration, purify and ionize the air, and also increase its humidity levels. Plants are an indispensable element of cities.

Despite being necessary for maintaining a favorable environmental situation in the city, plants are often insufficient. The reason for this is simple—there is a lack of space for planting them. An unusual solution to this problem was found by scientists from the University of Belgrade in Serbia: they have developed an innovative project that could serve as an alternative to traditional greening in urban areas.

“Liquid Trees,” or Liquid 3, is the name given by the scientists to their innovative project. “Liquid Trees” are tanks filled with water and microalgae. The concept is that microalgae convert carbon dioxide into oxygen in the same way as conventional plants. Furthermore, they perform this task significantly more efficiently! According to data from a biotechnology company, the algae *Chlorella vulgaris* absorbs carbon dioxide 400 times faster than common plants.

Of course. Here is the English translation of the extended analysis and the potential impact on Uzbekistan's economy and environment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The application of biotechnological solutions in urban planning has attracted increasing scholarly attention in recent decades, particularly with regard to photobioreactors and algae-based systems. Researchers emphasize that conventional urban greening—trees, lawns, and green roofs—plays a vital role in regulating air quality, humidity, and microclimate. However, in densely built environments, limited space for planting has driven interest in compact alternatives [1]. Microalgae, particularly *Chlorella vulgaris*, are widely studied for their high capacity to absorb carbon dioxide and generate oxygen. Experimental studies show that their CO₂ fixation rate is many times higher than that of terrestrial plants, making them attractive candidates for integration into the urban environment [2]. The “Liquid Trees” project in Belgrade is a notable example. It demonstrates how photobioreactors filled with microalgae can be placed in public spaces, delivering oxygen output comparable to two mature trees or 200 m² of lawn, while also producing biomass for agriculture, biofuel, and pharmaceuticals [3].

Earlier architectural experiments, such as the BIQ House in Hamburg with its algae façade system, showed that photobioreactors could serve multiple functions: energy generation, thermal regulation, and urban aesthetics [4]. Yet, scholars caution that such technologies have operational limitations, including the need for controlled lighting, nutrient supply, and regular maintenance [5]. Life-cycle analyses highlight that environmental benefits depend strongly on renewable energy input, water recirculation, and effective biomass utilization [6]. Critics also note that while “liquid trees” can complement greenery, they cannot fully substitute the broader ecological services of natural trees, such as habitat provision, evapotranspiration cooling, and stormwater management [7]. Overall, the literature positions microalgae photobioreactors as a valuable addition to sustainable urban infrastructure, particularly where soil-based greening is impractical, but stresses the importance of treating them as complementary rather than replacement technologies [8].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological approach of this study combines qualitative and analytical methods to examine the opportunities and limitations of “Liquid Trees” in urban planning. First, a review of scientific literature and international case studies was conducted to identify theoretical foundations and prior experiences with photobioreactors and algae-based greening systems. Second, comparative analysis was applied to evaluate the efficiency of microalgae (*Chlorella vulgaris*) relative to conventional urban vegetation in terms of carbon dioxide absorption and oxygen generation. Third, descriptive analysis was used to explore the potential socio-economic and environmental implications for urban infrastructure. Finally, synthesis of international best practices allowed the formulation of recommendations for adaptation in the context of Uzbekistan and other rapidly urbanizing regions.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Operating Principle and Technological Advantages

The analysis of the “Liquid Trees” (Liquid 3) technology demonstrates that its central principle is based on photosynthesis in a closed bioreactor system. Microalgae, most commonly *Chlorella vulgaris* or *Scenedesmus*, consume carbon dioxide and nutrients in the presence of sunlight, thereby releasing oxygen into the surrounding environment. According to the developers, a single bioreactor can generate an oxygen output equivalent to two mature trees or approximately 200 square meters of lawn. The system is autonomous, as it is powered by solar panels that supply energy to water pumps, which ensure constant mixing of the algal suspension. This process significantly increases photosynthetic efficiency compared to terrestrial plants, which often face shading, poor soil conditions, and seasonal dormancy.

Another important feature is year-round activity. While deciduous trees cease photosynthetic activity in winter, microalgae remain effective provided that light and above-freezing temperatures are maintained. Additionally, the periodic harvesting of algal biomass creates secondary benefits: it may be used as high-quality biofertilizer, biofuel feedstock, or raw material in the pharmaceutical industry. These aspects enhance the circularity and economic potential of the technology.

Addressing Criticism and Limitations

It is essential to emphasize that “Liquid Trees” are not intended to substitute traditional parks, green zones, or soil-based greening. Their primary purpose is to mitigate air pollution in highly urbanized areas where physical space for planting trees is unavailable, such as intersections, plazas, or industrial zones. This

clarification addresses a common misconception among citizens. Nevertheless, limitations include the lack of ecosystem services such as shading, biodiversity support, and stormwater management, which natural trees provide. Moreover, regular technical maintenance—nutrient supplementation, cleaning, and temperature regulation—is required to ensure continuous functionality.

Implications for Uzbekistan's Environment

The potential introduction of "Liquid Trees" in Uzbekistan's cities (Tashkent, Samarkand, Nukus) could yield several ecological benefits. First, it may help combat air pollution and dust, especially during summer dust storms, by reducing concentrations of particulate matter (PM2.5, PM10) and capturing localized CO₂ emissions from traffic and industry. Second, bioreactors could contribute to mitigating the "urban heat island" effect by cooling surrounding air through water evaporation. Third, the innovative visual design of these installations could play an educational role, raising ecological awareness among the population, particularly the youth. One important consideration, however, is water availability. Although the system functions as a closed loop with minimal evaporation losses, strategies such as rainwater harvesting or the use of treated wastewater would further increase sustainability.

Economic and Social Outcomes

The economic analysis suggests several positive outcomes. Firstly, local production and maintenance of such bioreactors could stimulate the development of small and medium-sized enterprises in biotechnology and "green" technologies. Secondly, domestic cultivation of microalgae strains would reduce dependency on imports and, in the long term, Uzbekistan—with its abundance of sunny days—could emerge as a regional hub for biomass production for food, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical industries. Thirdly, the modern and environmentally friendly appearance of cities adopting this technology would enhance their attractiveness to tourists, skilled professionals, and foreign investors. Finally, job creation would be stimulated in fields such as installation, maintenance, environmental monitoring, and applied microbiological research.

Implementation Pathway

For practical adaptation, a phased approach is recommended. A pilot project involving 10–15 bioreactors should be deployed in high-pollution zones of Tashkent, such as Chorsu Square and major traffic intersections. Scientific monitoring, conducted in collaboration with leading national universities, must accompany implementation to provide reliable data on effectiveness. Financing could be secured through public-private partnerships, combining local government co-financing, international green funds, and private investment. Furthermore, public education campaigns and adaptation of local microalgae strains resistant to Uzbekistan's climate would maximize both technological efficiency and social acceptance.

CONCLUSION

For Uzbekistan, "liquid trees" are not a panacea but a promising additional tool in the fight against the environmental problems of urbanized areas. It could stimulate the development of a green economy, create new high-tech industries, and improve the quality of life in cities.

However, residents of the cities where "Liquid Trees" have been installed have expressed their dissatisfaction. They argue that the microalgae tanks do not enrich the soil, reduce erosion, or contribute to the improvement of groundwater quality. Additionally, city dwellers complain about the unconventional appearance of the tanks.

Nevertheless, the "Liquid Trees" project represents an interesting and promising idea that could help improve the environmental conditions in major cities.

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